

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20800153

Influence Of Counselling Service On Senior Secondary School Student's Anti-Social Behaviours In Southern Senatorial Zone Of Taraba State, Nigeria

Queen Abah Peter; Bala A. Sule, Jerry Bala Habila; Grace Emmanuel

**Department of Education,
Kwararafa University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria
Corresponding author: graceemmaumell10@gmail.com**

Abstract

This study examined the influence of Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State, Nigeria, with a focus on academic, career, personal-social, behavioural, and group Counselling Service. Specifically, the study investigated the extent to which these counselling interventions mitigate disruptive behaviours such as truancy, aggression, bullying, and defiance. Five specific objectives and five research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, with a target population of 150,652 students from 355 public senior secondary schools in the state. Using a multistage sampling procedure, a sample of 398 students was drawn from 18 schools across Donga, Wukari, and Ibi Local Government Areas. Data was collected using the Counselling Service and Anti-social Behaviour Questionnaire (CSABQ), a structured four point Likert-scale instrument consisting of demographic and counselling service components. The instrument was validated by three experts in the College of Education, Kwararafa University, and its reliability was established through a pilot study involving 60 students, yielding a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.81. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer the research questions, and simple linear regression to test five null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance, using SPSS version 25.0. The findings revealed that Counselling Service significantly influenced the reduction of anti-social behaviours, with academic counselling recording a grand mean of 3.14, indicating improved study habits and reduced truancy. Regression analysis further confirmed varying levels of significant influence across the different Counselling Service. The study concludes that well-structured counselling programmes play a critical role in mitigating anti-social behaviour among secondary school students. It therefore recommends the recruitment and continuous training of professional school counsellors, strengthened stakeholder collaboration, and policy reinforcement by the Taraba State Ministry of Education to ensure effective integration of comprehensive Counselling Service within the school system.

Keywords: Counselling Service; Anti-Social Behaviours, Secondary Schools, Counsellors

INTRODUCTION

Education is universally recognized as a powerful tool for shaping human character, transmitting cultural values and preparing individuals for participation in society. Secondary education is important in adolescent development, particularly in the formative years when students undergo rapid biological, psychological and social changes (Hsieh *et al.*, 2023). At the secondary school level, students are expected to acquire not only academic skills but also the values, attitudes and behaviours that will guide them toward meaningful participation in the society. In recent years, educational systems across the

globe, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, have faced the rising challenge of anti-social behaviour among adolescent, a set of actions that violate social norms and disrupt the educational process (Onukwufor *et al.*, 2015). To address these challenges requires not only academic instruction but also robust psychosocial support services most notably, school counselling.

Counselling is a professional process that seeks to help individuals understand themselves, resolve personal challenges, make informed decisions and develop adaptive behaviours (Gibson & Mitchell, 2016). Within the school setting, guidance and Counselling Service serve as an essential component of the educational process. They aim to support students' academic, personal, social and career development while also providing intervention strategies for those exhibiting behavioural challenges (Högberg & Horn, 2022). According to Omoniyi (2016) school counselling is a professional service designed to promote the academic, career, emotional and social development of students. Counselling Service can help adolescents understand themselves, resolve conflicts, manage stress and develop adaptive behaviours. Effective counselling provides a safe space for self-expression, promotes social emotional learning and facilitates early intervention for behavioural issues.

In Nigeria, the integration of Counselling Service into the educational system was officially recognized with the establishment of the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013), which mandates the presence of guidance counsellors in secondary schools. Despite this policy, the implementation of effective counselling programmes remains inconsistent, particularly in public schools located in rural or underserved areas. Challenges such as inadequate staffing, poor funding, lack of counselling facilities and negative perceptions about counselling have hindered the delivery and effectiveness of these services (Agbaje, 2019). Omoniyi (2016) observed that students exposed to regular counselling showed better emotional regulation and less tendency to engage in fights or disobedience. Similarly, Okere *et al.* (2020) found that group counselling interventions significantly reduced instances of bullying, improved self-concept and fostered better peer relationships.

Anti-social behaviour is typically defined as conduct that violates societal norms, disrupts social harmony and infringes on the rights of others. Such behaviours include truancy, aggression, vandalism, theft, substance abuse and defiance of authority (Villafuerte-Díaz *et al.*, 2024; Farrington, 2015). Adolescents who engage in such behaviours often experience long term adverse consequences, including academic failure, social exclusion, mental health issues and eventual criminality (Khaliq & Rasool, 2019).

In school settings, anti-social behaviours are particularly disruptive. They manifest in multiple ways such as skipping classes, vandalizing school property, verbally abusing teachers, bullying peers and even engaging in physical altercations (Villafuerte-Díaz *et al.*, 2024). Studies have consistently shown a strong correlation between school dissatisfaction, academic stress and the prevalence of anti-social conduct (Löfstedt *et al.*, 2020; Halabi *et al.*, 2024). Anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students has become increasingly prevalent. Students across various states frequently exhibit behaviours that disrupt learning environments and lead to conflict with school authorities and peers (Olayinka, 2018; Ibrahim, 2020). The school environment is a reflection of broader societal problems, including insecurity, poverty, family instability and youth unrest. Consequently, the manifestation of anti-social behaviours in schools often reflects the psychological and social dislocations that young people experience in their immediate environments (Abdullahi, 2021).

The core problem confronting secondary schools in Taraba State is not merely the presence of anti-social behaviour, but the insufficient empirical evidence on the extent to which existing Counselling Service influence and potentially curb these behaviours. Therefore, this study investigated influence of Counselling Service on senior secondary school students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is suitable for systematically collecting data to describe, explain, and interpret the relationship between variables as they naturally occur. This design is considered appropriate because it allows for the collection of quantitative data from a representative sample of senior secondary school students to determine the extent to which Counselling Service influence their anti-social behaviour.

The population of this study comprised of all senior secondary school students in public secondary schools in Taraba State, Nigeria. The state consists of sixteen (16) Local Government Areas, with three hundred and fifty-five (355) public secondary schools distributed across twelve (12) education zones. There are one hundred and fifty thousand, six hundred and fifty-two (150,652) students in senior secondary schools in Taraba State (Taraba State Post Primary School Management Board (TSPPSMB), 2024) drawn from the three hundred and fifty-five (355) senior secondary schools.

The sample of three hundred and ninety-eight (398) senior secondary school students was obtained. Given the large and geographically dispersed nature of the population, a multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to ensure that the sample is a representative of the wider population while being logistically feasible for data collection. In the first stage, the researcher purposively selected the southern Taraba senatorial district which consist of three education zones, Donga (Donga LGA), Takum (Takum and Ussa LGAs) and Wukari (Ibi and Wukari LGAs) for the study for convenience and ease of data collection. Wukari, Ibi and Donga LGAs were used for the study.

The primary instrument that was used for data collection in this study was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured to capture quantitative data in line with the study’s descriptive survey design and to elicit responses that aligned with the research objectives. The instrument was titled “Counselling Service and Anti-Social Behaviour Questionnaire” (CSABQ) and was divided into six sections A – G.

Face and content validity was employed in this study. In order to make sure that the final copy of the questionnaire is valid for the study, the researcher employed the help of three experts from the College of Education, Kwararafa University Wukari, two from Guidance and Counselling and one from Measurement and Evaluation. The experts examined the clarity, relevance and comprehensiveness of the items, ensuring that each question reflected its corresponding construct. Based on their feedback, modifications were made to improve item wording, remove ambiguity, and enhance the overall layout and logical flow of the questionnaire.

The data collected for this study were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics to ensure the research objectives are adequately met. To answer the research questions, descriptive statistics, Mean and Standard Deviation, were employed. To test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance, Simple Linear Regression analysis was utilized. All statistical analyses were computed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Academic Counselling Service and Secondary School Anti-social Behaviours

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ Responses on Academic Counselling Service and Anti-social Behaviours

	Statement	N	Mean	Std. dev	Decision
1.	Academic counselling has helped me develop effective study habits	338	3.02	.871	Agree
2.	I have been able to set realistic academic goals with the help of a counsellor	338	3.30	.783	Agree
3.	Academic counselling has helped me overcome examination anxiety	338	3.07	.871	Agree
4.	I am less likely to skip classes because of academic support from a counsellor	338	3.10	.804	Agree
5.	Academic counselling has improved my motivation to perform well in school.	338	3.08	.817	Agree
6.	I feel more prepared for my future educational path due to academic counselling	338	3.28	.756	Agree
	Grand Mean	338	3.14		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 presents the response of the students on the influence of academic Counselling Service on their anti-social behaviour. The grand mean of 3.14 indicates that students generally agree that academic counselling contributes positively to their academic adjustment and reduces tendencies toward anti-social behaviour. Across the individual items, all the means range from 3.02 to 3.30, showing consistent agreement.

Career Counselling Service and Secondary School Anti-Social Behaviours

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ Responses on Career Counselling Service and Anti-social Behaviours

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
7.	Career counselling has helped me align my interests and abilities with future career paths.	338	3.66	.486	Agree
8.	I have received guidance on preparing for the labor market through career counselling.	338	3.51	.636	Agree
9.	Career counselling has helped me set clear goals for my future.	338	3.41	.747	Agree
10.	I am more focused on my future career because of counselling.	338	3.56	.497	Agree
11.	Career counselling has given me a sense of purpose, reducing my engagement in misbehaviour.	338	3.39	.816	Agree
12.	I believe a counsellor has provided me with useful information about occupational opportunities.	338	3.55	.498	Agree
	Grand mean	338	3.51		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 evaluated how career Counselling Service influence anti-social behaviour among students. The grand mean of 3.51, which is notably higher than that of academic counselling, indicates strong agreement among respondents that career counselling meaningfully contributes to reducing anti-social behaviours. All items have means ranging from 3.39 to 3.66, showing consistently positive perceptions.

Personal-Social Counselling Service and Secondary School Anti-social Behaviours

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ Responses on Personal-Social Counselling Service and Anti-social Behaviours

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
13.	Personal-social counselling has helped me manage my emotions effectively.	338	3.64	.480	Agree
14.	My relationships with peers have improved since I started personal-social counselling.	338	3.54	.571	Agree
15.	Counselling has helped me build my self-esteem.	338	3.39	.603	Agree
16.	I have learned how to resolve conflicts with others through counselling.	338	3.32	.538	Agree
17.	I am better able to cope with family and personal problems due to counselling.	338	3.50	.546	Agree
18.	Personal-social counselling has helped me deal with peer pressure.	338	3.24	.843	Agree
	Grand Mean	338	3.43		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 assessed students’ perceptions of personal-social Counselling Service. The grand mean of 3.43 indicates a high level of agreement that these services positively influence their social and emotional adjustment, which in turn reduces anti-social behaviour. Students reported that personal-social counselling helped them manage emotions effectively (Mean = 3.64), the highest score in the table.

Behavioural Counselling Service and Secondary School Anti-social Behaviours

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Responses on Behavioural Counselling Service

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
19.	Behavioural counselling has taught me how to replace bad habits with good ones.	338	3.07	.877	Agree
20.	Counselling has provided me with techniques to modify my undesirable conduct.	338	3.16	1.005	Agree
21.	I have learned to manage my anger through behavioural counselling.	338	3.33	.668	Agree
22.	Counselling has provided me with strategies to reduce defiance of authority.	338	2.99	1.018	Agree
23.	I am more responsible for my actions as a result of behavioural counselling.	338	3.30	.985	Agree
24.	Behavioural counselling has helped me understand the consequences of my actions.	338	3.35	.745	Agree
Grand Mean		338	3.20		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 examined the influence of behavioural Counselling Service on student behaviour. The grand mean of 3.20 showed general agreement among students that behavioural counselling contributes to reducing anti-social behaviour, although the agreement is weaker compared to career and personal-social counselling. The item means range from 2.99 to 3.35, showing moderate but positive perceptions.

Group Counselling Service and Secondary School Anti-social Behaviours

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Responses on Group Counselling Service

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
25.	Group counselling has helped me share experiences with peers who have similar issues.	338	3.49	.659	Agree
26.	I have learned problem-solving skills from other students in group counselling.	338	3.44	.638	Agree
27.	Group counselling sessions have helped me develop better peer relationships.	338	3.73	.443	Agree
28.	I am more cooperative with others because of group counselling.	338	3.02	1.115	Agree
29.	I feel more understood and less alone in my struggles because of group counselling.	338	3.54	.505	Agree
30.	Group counselling has provided me with a safe space to express myself.	338	3.19	.724	Agree
Grand Mean		338	3.40		Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5 presented students' perceptions of group Counselling Service. The grand mean of 3.40 indicates that students generally agree that group counselling contributes positively to reducing anti-social behaviour. The means range from 3.02 to 3.73. The highest score (3.73) relates to group counselling helping students develop better peer relationships, showing that peer interaction within a guided therapeutic environment promotes positive behaviour. Although the mean for improved cooperation is lower (3.02), it still indicates agreement that group counselling enhances social cooperation.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One: Academic Counselling Service have no significant influence on anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State.

Table 6: Regression analysis of influence of academic Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour of secondary school students.

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	25.560	.894	-	28.604	.000
Academic Counselling Service	.969	.283	.184	3.422	.001
Model Summary					
R	.184				
R ²	.034				
Adjusted R ²	.031				
F-Statistic	11.711				
ANOVA Sig.	.001				

P < 0.05

Table 6 showed that academic Counselling Service significantly influence anti-social behaviour among students. The regression coefficient B = .969 indicates that for every unit increase in academic counselling, anti-social behaviour decreases (or improves) by 0.969 units. The Beta value (β = .184) shows a positive but modest effect size. The p-value of .001 is below 0.05, indicating a statistically significant influence. The R value (0.184) and R² value (0.034) show that academic counselling accounts for 3.4% of the variation in anti-social behaviour. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that academic counselling significantly influences anti-social behaviour.

Hypothesis Two: Career Counselling Service have no significant influence on anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State.

Table 7: Regression analysis of influence of career Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour of secondary school students

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	24.130	1.146	-	21.054	.000
Career Counselling Service	.212	.054	.209	3.915	.000
Model Summary					
R	.209				
R ²	.044				
Adjusted R ²	.041				
F-Statistic	15.326				
ANOVA Sig.	.000				

P < 0.05

Table 7 revealed a significant influence of career Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour. The regression coefficient B = .212 indicates a positive change in behavioural outcomes with increased career counselling. The Beta value (β = .209) shows a modest but meaningful effect size, higher than that of academic counselling. The p-value (.000) is highly significant. The R value of .209 and R² of .044 show that career counselling explains 4.4% of changes in anti-social behaviour. The F-statistic (15.326, p = .000) confirms the significance of the model. This means that information about career goals, opportunities, and future paths help reduce anti-social behaviours. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing that career counselling significantly influences anti-social behaviour.

Hypothesis Three: Personal-social Counselling Service have no significant influence on anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State.

Table 8: Regression analysis of influence of personal-social Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour of secondary school students

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	19.982	1.238	-	16.145	.000
Personal-Social Counselling Service	.418	.060	.356	6.981	.000
Model Summary					
R	.356				
R ²	.127				
Adjusted R ²	.124				
F-Statistic	48.736				
ANOVA Sig.	.000				

P < 0.05

Table 8 showed a strong and significant influence of personal-social Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour. The regression coefficient B = .418 indicates a substantial improvement in behaviour with increased personal-social counselling. The Beta value ($\beta = .356$) is the highest among all counselling dimensions, implying that personal-social counselling has the strongest influence on behaviour. The p-value (.000) shows strong significance. The R value of .356 and R² of .127 indicate that personal-social counselling explains 12.7% of the variance in anti-social behaviour, which is a notable effect size in behavioural studies. The F-statistic (48.736, p = .000) confirms overall model significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, affirming that personal-social counselling has a significant and strong influence on anti-social behaviour among students.

Hypothesis Four: Behavioural Counselling Service have no significant influence on anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State.

Table 9: Regression analysis of influence of Behavioural Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour of secondary school students

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	25.296	.691	-	36.629	.000
Behavioural Counselling Service	.172	.036	.255	4.827	.000
Model Summary					
R	.255				
R ²	.065				
Adjusted R ²	.062				
F-Statistic	23.297				
ANOVA Sig.	.000				

P < 0.05

Table 9 revealed a significant influence of behavioural counselling on students' anti-social behaviour. The regression coefficient B = .172 and Beta ($\beta = .255$) show that behavioural counselling has a moderate effect on improving behaviour. The p-value (.000) indicates strong statistical significance. The R value (.255) and R² (.065) reveal that behavioural counselling explains 6.5% of behavioural changes. This shows that techniques such as reinforcement, modelling, and behaviour modification contribute significantly to reducing deviant behaviour. The F-statistic (23.297, p = .000) further supports the significance of the model. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Five: Group Counselling Service have no significant influence on anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State.

Table 10: Regression analysis of influence of Group Counselling Service on anti-social behaviour of secondary school students

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	27.817	.833	-	33.394	.000
Group Counselling Service	.039	.041	.052	.949	.343
Model Summary					
R	.052				
R ²	.003				
Adjusted R ²	.000				
F-Statistic	.901				
ANOVA Sig.	.343				

Table 10 revealed that group Counselling Service do not significantly influence anti-social behaviour. The regression coefficient $B = .039$ and Beta ($\beta = .052$) indicate a very weak influence. The p-value of .343 is greater than 0.05, showing that the effect is not statistically significant. The R value (.052) and R² (.003) indicate that group counselling accounts for only 0.3% of the variation in anti-social behaviour, which is negligible. The F-statistic (.901, $p = .343$) also shows that the model is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning group counselling does not significantly influence anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students in Taraba State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings showed that academic counselling has a significant, though modest, influence on anti-social behaviour among students. Students agreed that academic counselling helped improve study habits, reduce examination anxiety, motivate better performance, and minimize class skipping. This suggests that academic counselling plays a meaningful but not dominant role in reducing anti-social behaviour. This pattern is consistent with the work of Ogunlade and Aremu (2020), who found that academic counselling improved students' commitment to learning and reduced disruptive classroom conduct. Similarly, Okolie and Onah (2021) reported that students with access to strong academic support systems demonstrated fewer behavioural problems because academic achievement enhances self-esteem and reduces frustration which are two major predictors of anti-social behaviour.

This finding agrees with global research showing that adolescents who possess clarity about their future roles are less likely to engage in delinquency. Schwartz et al. (2020) career identity formation significantly reduces the likelihood of substance abuse, truancy, and school dropout among adolescents. Adom and Kwarteng (2019) reinforces the findings of Olatunji (2021), who argued that career clarity acts as a protective factor against hopelessness-induced behavioural problems in Nigerian youths.

Eze and Obi (2021) found that personal-social counselling significantly reduces aggression, lying, bullying, and defiance among secondary school students in Enugu State. Similarly, Olanrewaju et al. (2022) demonstrated that counselling interventions focusing on emotional intelligence and peer relationship management were associated with significant improvements in behaviour among students at risk of delinquency. Steinberg (2020) agreed that adolescence is a period marked by emotional turbulence and heightened susceptibility to peer influence. The positive findings of this study agree with the report of Iyiola and Salami (2020), who found that behavioural interventions significantly reduced truancy, bullying, and aggressive behaviour among secondary school boys in Lagos.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the influence of Counselling Service on senior secondary school students' anti-social behaviours in Taraba State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that academic counselling, career counselling, personal-social counselling and behavioural counselling all demonstrated significant positive influence on reducing anti-social behaviours among students. These forms of counselling helped students gain clarity, emotional stability, behavioural control and a sense of direction that collectively promotes healthier adjustment within the school environment. However, the study also found that group counselling

did not significantly influence anti-social behaviour, suggesting that contextual challenges such as cultural norms, facilitation quality, peer dynamics and institutional limitations may hinder its effectiveness. The results revealed the role that well-structured, professionally delivered Counselling Service play in promoting positive behaviour and supporting the holistic development of adolescents in Taraba State. Strengthening counselling systems in schools remains essential to helping students navigate academic pressure, emotional distress, peer influence and social instability that often contribute to behavioural problems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Schools in Taraba State should prioritise regular academic counselling sessions to help students develop effective study habits, manage academic stress and reduce frustration that often leads to anti-social behaviour.
- ii. The Ministry of Education and school authorities should ensure that career counselling programmes are well-developed and consistently delivered.
- iii. Given the strong influence of personal-social counselling on behavioural adjustment, counsellors should adopt structured emotional and social skills training.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, I. O. (2021). Examining Adolescent Anti-Social Behaviour in Kano State: A Qualitative Case Study. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research*, 4(1), 1-15.
- Adegoke, A. A., & Oladele, J. O. (2019). Group counselling as a strategy for reducing truancy and bullying among secondary school students. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 27(3), 112–128.
- Adom, D., & Kwarteng, A. O. (2019). The role of career guidance in curbing behavioural problems among senior high school students in Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(21), 16–27.
- Agbaje, M. O. (2019). Challenges and prospects of Counselling Service in public secondary schools in Ogun State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Foundations*, 10(2), 91–104.
- Eze, F. C., & Obi, C. N. (2021). The impact of personal-social counselling on reduction of aggressive behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Studies*, 28(1), 51–67.
- Farrington, D. P. (2015). The development of offending and antisocial behaviour from childhood: Key findings from the Cambridge study in delinquent development. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 36(6), 929–964.
- Folarin, O. A., Adeyemo, T. A., & Oladipo, S. E. (2022). Peer influence and adolescent behavioural outcomes: Implications for school counselling. *Nigerian Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 18(1), 23–38.
- Gibson, R. L., & Mitchell, M. H. (2016). *Introduction to counseling and guidance* (7th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson Education.
- Halabi, K. A., Shahrill, M., Roslan, R., & Adnan, M. (2024). The influence of impulsivity and anti-social behaviour on academic performance of university undergraduate students in Nigeria. *Jurnal Al-Sirat*, 24(1), 201-211.
- Högberg, B., & Horn, D. (2022). *Antisocial behaviour among adolescents and youth: Global and national trends*. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 25(2), 201–217.
- Hsieh, H. Y., Lin, H. L., & Chiu, C. Y. (2023). Mediating effect of emotional regulation between peer attachment and antisocial behaviour among adolescents. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 28(1), 1–14.
- Ibrahim, K. M. (2020). Relationship Between School Climate and Anti-Social Behaviour in Bauchi State. *Journal of Educational and Behavioural Sciences*, 11(3), 201-215.

- Iyiola, M. A., & Salami, O. (2020). Behaviour modification techniques and management of anti-social behaviours among male secondary school students in Lagos. *Journal of Behavioural Intervention and Education*, 12(3), 130–145.
- Khaliq, A., & Rasool, S. (2019). Causes of students' antisocial behaviour at secondary level schools. *The Spark: A HEC Recognized Journal*, 4, 116–148.
- Löfstedt, P., Backman, Y., & Larsson, L. (2020). School performance, family background and antisocial behaviour in Swedish adolescents. *Child Indicators Research*, 13(1), 137–154.
- Musa, I., & Shittu, T. (2021). Behavioural counselling strategies and reduction of defiant behaviours among secondary school students in Kwara State. *Journal of Educational Intervention*, 9(1), 60–75.
- National Policy on Education. (2013). *Federal Republic of Nigeria*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Nwafor, S. O., & Onyema, E. M. (2022). Group counselling and reduction of aggressive tendencies among adolescents in Anambra State. *International Journal of School Counselling*, 8(2), 33–49.
- Ogunlade, A. O., & Aremu, A. O. (2020). Academic counselling as a predictor of students' academic engagement and classroom behaviour. *Nigerian Journal of Counselling and Applied Psychology*, 6(1), 48–63.
- Okere, M. I. O., Anyanwu, I. E., & Akpan, B. E. (2020). Impact of group counselling on moral development of secondary school adolescents in Enugu State. *International Journal of Educational Psychology and Counselling*, 8(2), 93–108.
- Okolie, U. C., & Onah, E. L. (2021). Influence of academic guidance on students' deviant behaviour in secondary schools in Southeast Nigeria. *Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 11(4), 27–39.
- Olanrewaju, S. A., Ojelade, T. A., & Egbokhare, F. (2022). Emotional intelligence training and reduction of behavioural problems among secondary school students. *Journal of School Psychology in Africa*, 10(2), 102–118.
- Olatunji, F. (2021). Career uncertainty and behavioural problems among Nigerian adolescents: The moderating role of career counselling. *West African Journal of Educational Psychology*, 3(1), 55–70.
- Olayinka, B. A. (2018). Counselling intervention and discipline among students in public secondary schools in Oyo State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Administration and Planning*, 8(3), 41–52.
- Omoniyi, M. B. I. (2016). The role of guidance and counselling in effective teaching and learning in schools. *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 8(1), 12–17.
- Onukwufor, J. N., Iuloh, B. R., & Adiele, E. E. (2015). Causes and consequences of anti-social behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(18), 134–143.
- Schwartz, S. J., Waterman, A. S., & Syed, M. (2020). Emerging adulthood, identity development, and behavioural adjustment. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 49(2), 247–260.
- Steinberg, L. (2020). *Adolescence* (12th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Villafuerte-Díaz, A., De la Cruz-Cabanillas, M., & Palomares-Ruiz, A. (2024). School violence and antisocial behaviour: A meta-analysis of risk and protective factors. *Journal of School Health*, 94(2), 125-139.